

*Каньовська Л.В.,**Ляхович О.Д.**Буковинський державний медичний університет*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13337595>**РОЛЬ МІКРОЕЛЕМЕНТА ХРОМУ В РЕГУЛЯЦІЇ МЕТАБОЛІЗМУ ОРГАНІЗМУ ЛЮДИНИ***Kaniowska L.V.,**Liakhovych O.D.**Bukovinian State Medical University***THE ROLE OF THE TRACE ELEMENT CHROMIUM IN THE REGULATION OF THE METABOLISM OF THE HUMAN BODY****Анотація.**

Мікроелементний гомеостаз надзвичайно важливий для нормального функціонування організму людини. Хром є важливим мікроелементом, який відіграє роль у багатьох життєвоважливих функціях організму. Він необхідний для нормального функціонування метаболізму, а також для підтримки здоров'я серця, судин і м'язів, бере участь у багатьох біохімічних процесах, активує ряд ферментів, метаболізм жирів, підтримку балансу цукру в крові, функціонуванні щитоподібної залози, формуванні імунітету, а також впливає на ріст та регенерацію тканин. Водночас хром (як тривалентний, так і шестивалентний) у надлишковій кількості для організму людини є визнаним канцерогеном.

Abstract.

The homeostasis of trace elements is extremely important for the normal functioning of the human body. Chromium is an important trace element that plays a role in many vital body functions. It is necessary for the normal functioning of metabolism, as well as for maintaining the health of the heart, blood vessels and muscles, participates in many biochemical processes, activates a number of enzymes, fat metabolism, maintenance of blood sugar balance, functioning of the thyroid gland, formation of immunity, and also affects tissue growth and regeneration. At the same time, chromium (both trivalent and hexavalent) in excessive amounts for the human body is a recognized carcinogen.

Ключові слова: мікроелементи, хром, організм, метаболізм, глюкоза, функціонування.

Key words: trace elements, chromium, organism, metabolism, glucose, functioning.

Main part. Numerical studies have proven the role of element homeostasis in the functioning of the body, the presence of chemical elements in the form of many chemical compounds in all cells and tissues of the human body has been revealed. Mineral substances participate in the neutralization of acids and prevent the development of acidosis. They are important in normalizing water metabolism in the body. Biologically highly active connections of this group of substances with other nutrients were revealed. The role of mineral substances in hematopoiesis, tissue respiration and metabolism has been proven. In addition, the ability of most trace elements to "intervene" in the mechanism of cell death is beyond doubt [5].

One of the most important trace elements – chromium – exists in two valent forms: trivalent (Cr-III) and hexavalent chromium (Cr-VI). It is Cr-III that is commonly found in food and is a micronutrient. Salts of hexavalent chromium (chromium oxide, chromate) are highly toxic to humans and animals. The Nutrition Board of the National Institute of America in 2001 determined adequate daily doses of Cr-III for adults at 25-35 µg, indicating that a significant proportion of the population is not provided with this trace element. The materials of the Expert Group on Vitamins and Minerals (Expert Group on Vitamins and Minerals, Secretariat, August 2002) not only confirmed the need for widespread use of Cr-III as a preventive and therapeutic

agent, but also identified groups of diseases for the priority solution of this problem [5, 13].

Plants are a natural source of chromium for humans. Chromium is found in many vegetable crops (broccoli, green beans), berries and fruits, in some medicinal plants (shrimp, lemon balm), as well as in fish, shrimp, crabs, liver, chicken eggs, brewer's yeast and black pepper [17]. Absorption of chromium occurs mainly in the small intestine. In the tissues of the organs, the chromium content is ten times higher than in the blood. The largest amount of chromium is present in the liver (0.2 µg/kg) and kidneys (0.6 µg/kg), intestines, thyroid gland, cartilage and bone tissue, and in the lungs (in case of exposure to chromium compounds with air). Absorbed chromium is excreted from the body mainly through the kidneys (80%) and to a lesser extent through the lungs, skin and intestines (about 19%) [3].

Chromium is contained in food products in the form of inorganic salts, because of this, the absorption of this substance in the intestines does not exceed 25% of the total amount received with food. The bioavailability of chromium from inorganic compounds in the gastrointestinal tract is low, only 0.5-1%, but it increases to 20-25% when chromium is supplied in the form of complex compounds (picolinates, asparaginate). Hexavalent chromium is absorbed 3-5 times better than trivalent chromium. Up to 70% of the incoming

chromium settles in the lungs. With age, the amount of chromium in the body decreases [14].

There is more and more evidence that a number of diseases (diabetes, obesity, hypothyroidism, atherosclerosis, etc.) develop with chromium deficiency, and additional administration of this metal reduces the degree of insulin resistance. One of the biological effects of chromium is related to its influence on the so-called glucose tolerance factor, the activity of which decreases with a lack of chromium and is restored after the elimination of the deficiency of this substance in the body. It is now known that glucose tolerance factor (GTF) is trivalent chromium (Cr^{3+}) surrounded by two molecules of picolinic acid, which closely resembles nicotinic acid (vitamin B3) and three amino acids (probably glutamic acid, cysteine and glycine) was first discovered in brewer's yeast, which is one of the richest sources of organic chromium [19].

Glucose intolerance syndrome accompanies diabetes and manifests itself in the form of hyperglycemia and glucosuria against the background of chromium deficiency. There is a decrease in the absorption of glucose by the lens of the eye, the utilization of glucose for lipogenesis, an increase in the production of carbon dioxide, and a decrease in the synthesis of glycogen from glucose. All these disorders are eliminated by the introduction of chromium and insulin [20].

GTF may become one of the promising new natural antidiabetic agents. It effectively reduces elevated blood glucose levels in animals and humans with diabetes. It also lowers triglycerides and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol and increases high-density lipoprotein cholesterol in diabetic patients. These phenomena may be the result of lowering blood glucose and eliminating the conditions for the development of complications of type 2 diabetes. GTF treatment also prevents diabetes complications such as nephropathy and retinopathy. There is evidence that healthy adults given 200 mcg of chromium per day show a very significant reduction in total cholesterol [7, 20].

There is evidence that chromium enhances the action of insulin in peripheral cells. Chromium is able to influence the homeostasis of serum cholesterol and prevent its tendency to increase with age. Chromium deficiency in patients with diabetes is a controversial issue. The prevailing opinion is that serum chromium concentrations in such patients are low, so early long-term addition of chromium to standard therapy is recommended [1, 8].

In the study of the effect of chromium on insulin resistance, 34 patients with overweight and type 2 diabetes participated, who were divided into subgroups: with good and insufficient metabolic control. For 60 days, patients in both groups received 30 mcg of chromium picolinate as a dietary supplement; serum chromium concentration (using atomic absorption techniques), immunoreactive insulin level, and insulin resistance index were assessed at the beginning and end of the 2-month period [15].

Chromium concentration in serum in patients with type 2 diabetes was significantly lower than in healthy controls (2.18 ± 0.87 nmol/L vs. 4.03 ± 0.96 nmol/L,

$p < 0.001$). A significant decrease in the level of immunoreactive insulin and the index of insulin resistance was also found after the use of chromium at a dose of 30 μg per day (1 tablet of chromium picolinate) for 2 months. The effects of this trace element consist in potentiating the action of insulin, improving the first phase of insulin secretion, and increasing postreceptor sensitivity to insulin. The inclusion of chromium in the early complex therapy of type 2 diabetes helps to reduce the degree of insulin resistance [15, 16].

Experimental data show that metabolic processes at the cellular level and the speed of aging processes largely depend on the content of Cr^{3+} in the blood [16]. With a deficiency of Cr^{3+} in the body, the level of glucose in the blood increases, which is accompanied by an increase in the number of free radicals and the destructive effect of oxidative stress. That is, a high level of glucose in the blood triggers the body's aging mechanisms. Chromium deficiency and elevated blood glucose levels lead to another very serious pathology - a violation of protein metabolism and the permeability of cell membranes.

In particular, a high level of glucose in the blood affects the collagen of blood vessels, as a result of which its structure and elastic properties are disturbed. During a change in the structure of collagen, the structure and function of the connective tissue in the walls of blood vessels, vertebrae, joints, hair, and nails is disturbed. In addition, in the conditions of increased level of glucose in the blood and reduced transportation of it into the cells, the supply of energy to the cells is disturbed. At the same time, chronic fatigue syndrome develops in the body of humans and animals, and vitality decreases [18].

Chromium is one of the trace elements that affect the functional activity of the immune system and increase the body's resistance to diseases. The body's immune function can be impaired in the absence of Cr^{3+} , because under such conditions, the content of corticosteroids in the blood increases, which suppress the immune system, which, apparently, occurs through the indirect effect of cytokines [2, 6].

Chromium is able to influence the homeostasis of serum cholesterol and prevent its tendency to increase with age. Chromium deficiency in animals impairs the ability to incorporate amino acids glycine, serine, methionine and amino-isobutyric acid into the heart muscle. Chromium does not affect the metabolism of other amino acids [3].

During pregnancy, there is a significant decrease in the concentration of chromium in hair and urine. The level of chromium in the hair is also reduced in premature babies and prevents full development. A decrease in the content of chromium and an increase in its excretion with urine was noted with increased physical exertion in athletes. An indicator of the supply of the human body is the daily excretion of chromium in the urine (normally 5-10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$) [11].

Chromium is found in many vegetables, berries and fruits, medicinal plants, as well as many food products, but eating such products will not be able to fully replenish the required amount of this trace element. This is due to the small content of chromium in the

listed products and its low digestibility. To date, nutritional supplements have been developed (the most effective of them are based on chromium picolinate and chromium histidine), which allow reducing the deficiency of chromium in the human body [10].

Chromium picolinate is the most active form of this trace element. It is formed by trivalent chromium and three molecules of picolinic acid. This compound has a wide pharmacological effect, but its most interesting effect is considered to be the treatment of depression. A study conducted on 113 patients found that daily intake of 600 mcg of chromium picolinate significantly reduced cravings for carbohydrates due to bad mood. Also, this drug eliminates such symptoms as mood swings, fatigue and indifference to gaining excess weight [2, 9].

The paradox of the effect of chromium on the human body is that it is necessary for the vital activity of the body, but also exhibits toxic properties [9]. A large number of chromium compounds have been analyzed for genotoxicity under in vitro and natural conditions. In these studies, various properties of compounds were taken into account: degree of oxidation, solubility, ability to penetrate through cell membranes and interact with cellular components, stability in the intracellular environment. It has been established that most compounds of hexavalent chromium are genotoxic, which is due to their solubility and bioavailability, that is, the ability to penetrate into target cells [17].

The analysis of the data presented in the article allows us to conclude that the trace element chromium affects the human body, and can be used in the form of biologically active additives to correct a number of various disorders. Chromium supplements may be beneficial for people who are at increased risk of chromium deficiency, such as those with type 2 diabetes, obesity, or other chronic conditions.

References

1. Zahorodnii VV, Yaroslavs'ka LP. Funktsional'ne kharchuvannia – yak skladova zdorovoho sposobu zhyttia [Functional nutrition is a component of a healthy lifestyle]. V: Materialy pershoi mizhn. nauk.-prakt. konf. Intehratsiini ta innovatsiini napriamky rozvytku kharchovoi industrii; 2017 Zhov 19-20; Cherkasy. Cherkasy; 2017. T.1; s. 128-33. (in Ukrainian)

2. Setko AH, Kashtanova SH, Trishyna SP. Osoblyvosti funktsionuvannia orhaniv ta system studentiv medychnoho vuzu pry nedostatnii nutriientnii zabezpechenosti [Peculiarities of the functioning of organs and systems of medical university students with insufficient nutrient supply]. Zdorov'ia naseleння ta navkolyshnie seredovysche. 2013;6(243):7-9. (in Ukrainian)

3. Marushko YuV, Kostyns'ka NH, Hyschak TV, Marushko TV. Biolohichna rol' khromu i vplyv zmin yoho vmistu na perebih ozhyrinnia ta arterial'noi hipertenzii v ditei (ohliad literatury, vlasni doslidzhennia) [The biological role of chromium and the effect of changes in its content on the course of obesity and arterial hypertension in children (literature review, own research)]. Suchasna pediatria. Ukraina.

2022;3(123):73-9. doi: 10.15574/SP.2022.123.73 (in Ukrainian)

4. Akhtar A, Dhaliwal J, Saroj P, Uniyal A, Bishnoi M, Sah SP. Chromium picolinate attenuates cognitive deficit in ICV-STZ rat paradigm of sporadic Alzheimer's-like dementia via targeting neuroinflammatory and IRS-1/PI3K/AKT/GSK-3 β pathway. Inflammopharmacology. 2020;28(2):385-400. doi: 10.1007/s10787-019-00681-7

5. Dubey P, Thakur V, Chattopadhyay M. Role of Minerals and Trace Elements in Diabetes and Insulin Resistance. Nutrients [Internet]. 2020 Jun[cited 2024 May 22];12(6):1864. Available from: <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-6643/12/6/1864> doi: 10.3390/nu12061864

6. Dworzański W, Sembratowicz I, Cholewińska E, Tutaj K, Fotschki B, Juskiewicz J, et al. Effects of Different Chromium Compounds on Hematology and Inflammatory Cytokines in Rats Fed High-Fat Diet. Front Immunol [Internet]. 2021 Feb[cited 2024 May 22];12:614000. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/immunology/articles/10.3389/fimmu.2021.614000/full> doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2021.614000

7. Dzhuriak VS, Bondarchuk IV, Sydoruk LP, Sem'ianiv MM, Repchuk YuV, Kryklyvets' LH, ta in. Ryzyk vynykennia khronichnoi khvoroby nyrok ta tsukrovoho diabetu u khvorykh na arterial'nu hipertenziiu [The risk of chronic kidney disease and diabetes mellitus in patients with arterial hypertension]. Simeina medytsyna. 2017;2:51-4. doi: 10.30841/2307-5112.2(70).2017.115031 (in Ukrainian)

8. Gabel K, Hoddy KK, Varady KA. Safety of 8-h time restricted feeding in adults with obesity. Appl Physiol Nutr Metab. 2019;44(1):107-9. doi: 10.1139/apnm-2018-0389

9. World Health Organization. Tenfold increase in childhood and adolescent obesity in four decades: new study by Imperial College London and WHO [Internet]. 2017 [updated 2017 Oct 11; cited 2024 May 21]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/ru/news/item/11-10-2017-tenfold-increase-in-childhood-and-adolescent-obesity-in-four-decades-new-study-by-imperial-college-london-and-who>

10. Guarneri F, Costa C, Cannavò SP, Catania S, Bua GD, Fenga C, et al. Release of nickel and chromium in common foods during cooking in 18/10 (grade 316) stainless steel pots. Contact Dermatitis. 2017;76(1):40-8. doi: 10.1111/cod.12692

11. Heshmati J, Omani-Samani R, Vesali S, Maroufizadeh S, Rezaeinejad M, Razavi M, et al. The Effects of Supplementation with Chromium on Insulin Resistance Indices in Women with Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Randomized Clinical Trials. Horm Metab Res. 2018;50(3):193-200. doi: 10.1055/s-0044-101835

12. Hyschak TV, Marushko YuV. Fazy adaptatsii u ditei iz pervynnoiu arterial'noiu hipertenziiu [Adaptation phase in children with primary hypertension]. Suchasna pediatria. Ukraina. 2016;7(79):88-93. doi: 10.15574/SP.2016.79.88 (in Ukrainian)

13. Imanparast F, Javaheri J, Kamankesh F, Rafiei F, Salehi A, MollaaliakZ, et al. The effects of chromium and vitamin D3 co-supplementation on insulin resistance and tumor necrosis factor-alpha in type 2 diabetes: a randomized placebo-controlled trial. *Appl Physiol Nutr Metab.* 2020;45(5):471-7. doi: 10.1139/apnm-2019-0113
14. Islam GMR, Rahman MM, Hasan MI, Tadesse AW, Hamadani JD, Hamer DH. Hair, serum and urine chromium levels in children with cognitive defects: A systematic review and meta-analysis of case control studies. *Chemosphere [Internet].* 2022 Mar[cited 2024 May 21];291(2):133017. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0045653521034895?via%3Dihub> doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.133017
15. Khodavirdipour A, Haddadi F, Keshavarzi S. Chromium Supplementation; Negotiation with Diabetes Mellitus, Hyperlipidemia and Depression. *J Diabetes Metab Disord.* 2020;19(1):585-5. doi: 10.1007/s40200-020-00501-8
16. Kooshki F, Tutunchi H, Vajdi M, Karimi A, Niakar HR, Shoorei H, et al. A Comprehensive insight into the effect of chromium supplementation on oxidative stress indices in diabetes mellitus: A systematic review. *Clin Exp Pharmacol Physiol.* 2021;48(3):291-309. doi: 10.1111/1440-1681.13462
17. Lari A, Fatahi S, Sohoul MH, Shidfar F. The Impact of Chromium Supplementation on Blood Pressure: A Systematic Review and Dose-Response Meta-Analysis of Randomized-Controlled Trials. *High Blood Press Cardiovasc Prev.* 2021;28(4):333-42. doi: 10.1007/s40292-021-00456-8
18. Marushko Yu, Tarynska O. The level of chrome in children's hair. *Actual Problems of Pediatrics, Obstetrics and Gynecology.* 2014;2:47-49.
19. Molz P, Molz WA, Dallemole DR, Weber A, Salvador M, Pra D, et al. Potential Ameliorative Effects of Chromium Supplementation on Glucose Metabolism, Obesity, and Genomic Stability in Prediabetic Rat Model. *Biol Trace Elem Res.* 2021;199(5):1893-9. doi: 10.1007/s12011-020-02299-1
20. Moradi F, Maleki V, Saleh-Ghadimi S, Kooshki F, Gargari BP. Potential roles of chromium on inflammatory biomarkers in diabetes: A Systematic. *Clin Exp Pharmacol Physiol.* 2019;46(11):975-83. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1440-1681.13144>